

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Biocompatible magnetic gelatin nanoparticles with enhanced MRI contrast performance prepared by single-step desolvation method

To cite this article: C Teijeiro-Valiño *et al* 2021 *Nano Ex.* 2 020011

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Synthesis of fish gelatin nanoparticles and their application for the drug delivery based on response surface methodology](#)
Deni Subara, Irwandi Jaswir, Maan Fahmi Rashid Alkhatib et al.
- [An innovative co-axial system to electrospin *in situ* crosslinked gelatin nanofibers](#)
Chiara Gualandi, Paola Torricelli, Silvia Panzavolta et al.
- [Mechanical properties and *in vitro* behavior of nanofiber–hydrogel composites for tissue engineering applications](#)
Dan Kai, Molamma P Prabhakaran, Benjamin Stahl et al.

PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

RECEIVED

28 December 2020

REVISED

26 March 2021

ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION

7 April 2021

PUBLISHED

26 April 2021

Original content from this work may be used under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence.

Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

Biocompatible magnetic gelatin nanoparticles with enhanced MRI contrast performance prepared by single-step desolvation method

C Teijeiro-Valiño^{1,4}, M A González Gómez^{1,4}, S Yáñez¹, P García Acevedo¹, A Arnosa Prieto¹, S Belderbos^{2,3}, W Gsell^{2,3}, U Himmelreich^{2,3}, Y Piñeiro¹ and J Rivas^{1,*}

¹ Department of Applied Physics, Nanotechnology and Magnetism Laboratory (NANOMAG), Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain

² Biomedical MRI, Department of Imaging and Pathology, KU Leuven, O&N I, Herestraat 49—box 505, 3000 Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

³ Molecular Small Animal Imaging Center (MoSAIC), KU Leuven, O&N I, Herestraat 49—box 505, 3000 Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

⁴ These authors equality contributed to the preparation of this manuscript.

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: carmen.teijeiro@usc.es, manuelantonio.gonzalez@usc.es, susana.yanez@usc.es, pelayo.garcia.acevedo@usc.es, angela.arnosa@usc.es, y.pineiro.redondo@usc.es, jose.rivas@usc.es, sarah.belderbos@kuleuven.be, willy.gsell@kuleuven.be and uwe.himmelreich@kuleuven.be

Keywords: nanoparticles, gelatin, magnetite, magnetic resonance imaging

Abstract

Magnetic nanoparticles are versatile materials that have boosted the development of different biomedical applications, being superparamagnetic magnetite nanoparticles a milestone in the field, after achieving clinical approval as contrast agents in magnetic resonance imaging (Feridex[®]), magnetic hyperthermia agents for oncological treatments (NanoTherm[®]), or iron deficiency supplement (Feraheme[®]). However, its potential as theragnostic agent could be further expanded by its encapsulation within a biodegradable hydrogel, capable of enhancing the biocompatibility and loading abilities, to simultaneously carry drugs, radiotracers, or biomolecules. Gelatin, is a natural biopolymer with optimal *in vivo* feature and gelling capacity that has been extensively used for decades in pharmaceuticals. In this work, we have addressed the preparation of gelatin nanoparticles, bare and loaded with magnetite nanoparticles, with controlled size to be used as contrast agents in magnetic resonance imaging. The main formulation parameters influencing the preparation of gelatin nanoparticles with controlled size by single-step desolvation method, were studied and optimized, to produce small gelatin nanoparticles (97nm) and highly loaded (38% w/w) Fe₃O₄@citrate gelatin nanoparticles (150 nm) with high magnetic response (65emu/g). The viability assays of the magnetic gelatin nanoparticles, tested with mesenchymal stem cells, showed negligible toxicity and *in vitro* magnetic resonance imaging tests, performed in agar phantoms, revealed a good contrast for T2 weighting MRI, $r_2 = 265.5(\text{mM}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$, superior to commercial products, such as Resovist or Endorem.

1. Introduction

The development of nanomaterials with designed abilities has witnessed an intense research in the last years. Based on the control achieved at chemical level, the production of nanomaterials can be afforded combining hybrid inorganic/organic phases [1] and designed properties only observable at the nanoscale like enhanced selective catalytic/photocatalytic activities [2, 3], tailored plasmonic response [4], size-dependent fluorescence [5], or superparamagnetic (SPM) behaviour [6], among others. This key-enabling technology is opening the door to a plethora of innovative applications that are permeating different fields from energy, spintronics, environmental remediation technologies to biotechnology or biomedicine. More particularly, nanobiomedicine benefits from the similarity of scales shared by nanoparticles (NPs) and relevant biological entities such as viruses, cells or bacteria. For this reason, the development of complex nanomaterials, that can be designed to interact locally with biological processes, has delivered new diagnostic and therapeutic paradigms and new tools

for probing the complex fundamentals of our biological mechanisms [7]. As a result of these efforts, several soft organic nanostructures, mainly liposomes, nano-emulsions or solid lipid NPs, formed by non-covalent interactions and capable of encapsulating hydrophilic or lipophilic drugs [8], have been approved for clinical uses as vaccines, antifungal, anaesthetics, or antibiotics [9]. However, the general stability of these structures under different biological conditions (pH, pressure in blood stream, tissues stiffnesses, etc) highly depends on the use of an external surfactant coating which poses a challenge for *in vivo* applications [10].

In parallel, inorganic nanomaterials have been also developed for theragnostic applications with very successful outcomes. Superparamagnetic magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles are a paradigmatic case of versatility and success after having been clinically tested and approved for commercialization as enhanced contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (Feridex, Resovist, Ferumoxtran-10) [11], as iron deficiency therapeutics (Feraheme[®]) or magnetic hyperthermia therapies for brain tumour treatment (NanoTherm[®]) [12]. However, there is an urgent need to develop multimodal theragnostic agents that maximize the advantages offered by different aspects of designed nanomaterials, such as target-specific delivery of multimodal imaging and therapeutic agents [13]. Designing such complex nanostructures involves the simultaneous encapsulation of theragnostic moieties with different physicochemical nature like stiff inorganic cores (Fe_3O_4 NPs as MRI contrast agents) or organic molecules (drugs, plasmids, etc) within a single nanovector, together with the conjugation of different species (radiotracers for PET imaging, biomolecules like antibodies or growth factors) on its external surface. In addition to a successful chemical engineering of hierarchical synthetical procedures, the final theragnostic agent requires to show overall chemical stability, structural resistance when exposed to stiff biological environments, like the extra cell matrix of tumours [7] or the blood brain barrier [8], and biodegradability at medium time term for clearance purposes.

The selection of the hosting material for such complex nanostructures is crucial, and although liposomes or soft colloids are versatile systems for drug loading, their limited stability in biological media prevents them from complex engineering procedures for multimodal theragnostic applications [14]. In this regard, gelatin, a linear biopolymer obtained from partial acid (Type A) or alkaline (Type B) hydrolysis of animal collagen, a cost-effective and very abundant source, is one of the most versatile natural biopolymers, capable of forming an hydrogel with suitable physicochemical properties for biomedical applications. Above a melting temperature (approximately 30 °C) it can be dissolved in water as individual polymer coils while undergoes a reversible gelation at low temperatures forming a viscoelastic macroscopic hydrogel, with versatile elastohydronechanical properties [9]. Gelatin has been extensively used for decades as component in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and food products, under the consideration of Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) material by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [10]. Gelatin combines biocompatibility, biodegradability, low-immunogenicity [15], ability to modulate cell adhesion and improved internalization [16] thanks to its Arg-Gly-Asp (RGD) sequences and a rich chemical surface densely crowded with carboxylate and amine groups, which facilitate the grafting of diverse targeting ligands [17]. All these physicochemical features make gelatin an ideal molecule for the association of hydrophilic therapeutic biomolecules, such as antigens, nucleic acids, RNA or peptides [15, 18, 19] or contrast agents like magnetite NPs for diagnostic applications using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), that are generating a great interest in the use of gelatin nanoparticles for theragnostic applications.

Gelatin nanoparticles (GNPs) can be prepared by conventional emulsification techniques, where a mixture of gelatin water solution with a non-miscible organic phase containing a high concentration of surfactants is submitted to a high energy homogenization process inducing nanoparticle formation [20–23]. Also, it has been reported a modified water-in-water emulsification process using poloxamer as emulsifying agent under mild conditions to produce nanoparticles [24]. In the layer by layer technique, a gelatin solution is incubated with preformed nanoparticles of opposite electrostatic charge, to promote the electrostatic adsorption of gelatin onto nanoparticles surface [25, 26]. Moreover, by using self-assembly methods, gelatin modified with hydrophobic molecules, either by chemical modification or by the formation of electrostatic complexes, can self-assemble in aqueous environments to form micelles [27, 28]. However, the most frequently used method by far is the desolvation technique which does not require high energy as in emulsification processes, and happens under soft conditions, avoiding high concentrations of surfactant or chemical reactions. Hereby, gelatin must be dissolved at a pH far from its isoelectric point, to promote electrostatic charging, reducing hydrophobic intramolecular interactions which leads to protein unfolding. Once gelatin molecules are individually dispersed, the addition of a desolvent agent like acetone, ethanol or sodium sulfate, produces the controlled nanoprecipitation of gelatin in form of nanoparticles [29–31]. Due to the very broad molecular weight distribution of most commercial gelatins, a previous desolvation step is usually required to discard the low molecular weight gelatin fraction, ensuring the stability and homogeneity of nanoparticles. For this reason, the desolvation method is usually performed in two-steps. Upon gelatin nanoparticle formation, a crosslinking step has to be performed to prevent the disintegration of GNPs in aqueous media [32]. Although different crosslinking agents such as formaldehydes [33–37], genipin, a natural crosslinker extracted from gardenia fruit [38, 39], mixtures of

carbodiimide and N-hydroxysuccinimide [31] or recombinant microbial transglutaminase [40] can be found in the literature, glutaraldehyde, a specific type of formaldehyde, has been most frequently employed due to its efficacy at low concentrations that results in very stable nanoparticles.

Despite the successful association of different drugs, proteins or biological moieties [15, 18, 19, 41] to GNPs, the intrinsic heterogeneity of gelatin produces the appearance of large aggregates, therefore the preparation of reproducible GNPs with tailored size and narrow size distribution remains a challenge [42]. This problem increases further when preparing multifunctional GNPs loaded with stiff inorganic NPs. Hereby, limited size control and a wide size distribution poses severe limitations for *in vivo* applications. In this regard, magnetite loaded gelatin nanoparticles (MGNPs) with tailored size would benefit from all the inherited advantages of both materials for biomedical applications. Magnetite NPs, are one of the most used magnetic materials [43] in theragnostic, biodetection and regeneration applications [6, 44, 45] and have already been approved for clinical uses as discussed previously.

Based on this background information, the objectives of this work were; (i) to optimize the main formulation parameters for the preparation of gelatin nanoparticles by one-step desolvation method, (ii) the synthesis of different superparamagnetic Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles by co-precipitation method, (iii) the preparation of Fe_3O_4 loaded gelatin nanoparticles using the previously synthesized magnetite nanoparticles in the optimized conditions and (iv) the proof of concept of their bioapplication as diagnostic agent by the performance of a magnetic resonance imaging phantom and a cellular toxicity study.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials

The molecular weight monodisperse gelatin PH3226 was kindly donated by Gelita (GELITA, IA, United States). Glutaraldehyde ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$) water solution at 25% was purchased from Acros Organics-Thermo Fisher (Fisher Scientific, The Hague, Netherlands). Genipin (Methyl (1S,2R,6S)-2-hydroxy-9-(hydroxymethyl)-3-oxabicyclo [4.3.0]nona-4,8-diene-5-carboxylate, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$) was obtained from FUJIFILM Wako Chemicals (Fujifilm Wako Chemicals U.S.A. Corp. Richmond, USA). HCl solution at 37% was obtained from Fisher (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). NaOH was purchased from Merck (Merck, KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). Acetone reagent grade and ethanol absolute were purchased from Scharlau (Scharlau Pure Chemicals, Scharlau Chemie, S.A, Barcelona, Spain). Iron(III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%), iron (II) sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%), dopamine hydrochloride (DA, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$, powder), sodium citrate dihydrate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{Na}_3\text{O}_9 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%), chitosan (CS, deacetylated chitin, low molecular weight), polyacrylic acid (PAA, $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_n$ with molecular weight average MW1800), ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 28%), agar ($(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_9)_n$, powder) and phosphate buffer saline (PBS) were all obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA). High-glucose Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) containing GlutaMax, fetal bovine serum (FBS), and penicillin-streptomycin were obtained from Gibco-Invitrogen (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). RealTime-GloTM MT Cell Viability Assay was obtained from Promega Corporation (Promega Biotech ibérica S.L. Madrid, Spain). MilliQ (Millipore[®], Merck, KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) deionized water was used in all the experiments. Mouse mesenchymal stem cells (mMSCs) were obtained from the laboratory of Stem Cell Biology and Embryology at KU Leuven (Belgium).

2.2. Synthetic procedure for nanoparticles preparation

2.2.1. Optimization of gelatin nanoparticles (GNPs) by 1-step desolvation method

First, a water solution of gelatin at a concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} was prepared at 37°C , after complete dissolution, the pH of this water phase was adjusted to 2.5 using HCl 0.1M. Then, 7ml of gelatin solution was thermostated at 50°C using a silicone bath and put under mechanical stirring using a glass rod (800rpm), next, 21ml of acetone was directly added as a bulk into the water phase. Immediately, 100 μL of glutaraldehyde solution (25% w/v) was added to the mixture and left within an incubator (IKA® KS4000) overnight at 37°C with horizontal shaking (175rpm). Next day, 5ml of the formulation were isolated by centrifugation at 7830g, for 99 min at room temperature. Then, the solvents were discarded and the yellow-transparent GNPs located at the bottom were redissolved in 2ml of PBS.

The formulation parameters were optimized in the order shown in figure 1, changing only one single parameter in each experiment while the other variables were kept constant. Once we have selected an optimal condition for one formulation parameter, we fixed this value and continue with the next parameter.

2.3. Preparation of magnetite nanoparticles (MNPs)

Fe_3O_4 NPs were obtained by a co-precipitation method [46, 47] with some modifications. To this end, two iron salts providing Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions, $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (45 mmol) and $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (30 mmol) were dissolved in 100 ml of an 10mM HCl aqueous solution, under mechanical stirring. The mixture was heated at 60°C , and NH_4OH (770 mmol) was added subsequently to produce small Fe_3O_4 NPs (10 nm). At this point, a polymer can be added to the NPs solution to produce coated NPs. For the present work we have developed a set of NPs with different coating polymers, Sodium citrate, Chitosan (CS), Polyacrylic acid (PAA) or Dopamine (PDA), which were added in a ratio 1.11 mmol, and left for 1 h of incubation at 60°C . Then, the coated magnetic nanoparticles were acidified up to pH 5 with the incorporation of the HCl solution at 9%. Polymer coated magnetite NPs were separated from the reaction medium by a magnetic field and washed several times (6x) with MilliQ water. Finally, Fe_3O_4 @Polymer NPs were redispersed in MilliQ water to be used in the preparation of magnetic gelatin NPs.

2.3.1. Preparation of magnetic gelatin nanoparticles (MGNPs)

Fe_3O_4 loaded gelatin nanoparticles were prepared using the synthesized magnetite NPs described in the previous section. The first step of the procedure, involves the sonication of a water suspension of MNPs at a concentration of 0.72 mg ml^{-1} for 5 min in a Branson Sonifier (Output 1, duty cycle 95%) for ensuring the total dispersion of MNPs. After that, the MNPS solution was immediately incorporated into an equal volume of the gelatin aqueous phase at a concentration of 40 mg ml^{-1} . Then the desolvation method was carried out with the optimal formulation conditions ($T = 37^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 3.5$, gelatin concentration = 20 mg ml^{-1} , $V_{\text{water}}/V_{\text{acetone}} = 1:3$, $\text{mass}_{\text{glutaraldehyde}}/\text{mass}_{\text{gelatin}} = 0.179$) established in our optimization study as described with detail in section 3.1.1 by applying the experimental steps detailed in section 2.2.1. Finally, the magnetite gelatin NPS were obtained and isolated magnetically with the help of an external permanent magnet (NdFeB) for 24h. The supernatant was discarded and magnetic-gelatin nanoparticles were dispersed in 2ml of PBS.

2.4. Physicochemical characterization of nanoparticles

2.4.1. Dynamic light scattering

Mean particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of GNPs were determined by photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS). Samples were diluted in MilliQ Water and the analysis was carried out at 25°C with an angle detection of 173° . Zeta potential measurements were performed by laser Doppler anemometry (LDA). PCS and LDA analysis were performed with at least 3 replicates of NPs per each condition condition using a NanoZS® (Malvern Instruments, Malvern, UK).

2.4.2. Morphological characterization

The morphology of MNPs and MGNPs was studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a JEOL JEM-1011 microscope operating at 100 kV (JEOL, Tokyo, Japan). To this end, a drop of diluted sample was placed on copper grids with Formvar® films and was let dry for one day prior to the characterization.

2.4.3. Structural characterization

The characterization of the crystalline phases of MNPs was performed by x-ray diffraction (XRD), for this, powder samples were analyzed using a Philips PW1710 diffractometer (Panalytical, Brighton, UK) with a $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation source, $\lambda = 1.54186 \text{ \AA}$. Measurements were collected in the 2Θ angle range between 10° and 80° with a step size of 0.02° and counting time of 10 s per step on powder samples. The JCPDS (Joint Committee on

Powder Diffraction Standards) powder diffraction database was used for the qualitative phase analyses of the XRD patterns.

2.4.4. Chemistry characterization

Surface functional groups of dried MNPs particles were analysed by Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy with a Thermo Nicolet Nexus spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain) using the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) method from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . The percentage of organic and magnetic material of MNPs and GMNPs was analysed using thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) using a Perkin Elmer model 7 (Perkin, Waltham, MA, USA) analyzer from 25 °C to 850 °C (with a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1}) in nitrogen gas (N_2).

2.4.5. Magnetic characterization

The magnetic response of lyophilized samples of MNPs and MGMPs was performed using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) (DMS/ADE Technologies, Massachusetts, USA) at room temperature with applied magnetic fields between -10 and 10 kOe. Magnetization data were normalized to the amount of magnetite mass for each sample (determined by flame atomic absorption spectroscopy, FAAS), assuming all the iron present in the sample exists as Fe_3O_4 . To obtain precise measurements more than 5 mg of dried samples were measured each time.

2.5. Biological characterization

2.5.1. Preparation and acquisitions of MRI phantoms

To demonstrate the T_2 and T_1 effects exhibited by MGMPs in agar-aqueous solution, six different samples of MGMPs were prepared ($6.21 \cdot 10^{-2}$, $3.10 \cdot 10^{-2}$, $6.21 \cdot 10^{-1}$, $3.10 \cdot 10^{-1}$ and $6.21 \cdot 10^{-1}$ mM of iron concentration), GNPs were used as control (0 mM of Fe). For this purpose, MGMPs were resuspended in equal amounts of PBS and 2% agar in 200 μl Eppendorf tubes. These tubes were placed into a cylindrical Teflon holder (7 cm of outer diameter and 3.5 cm of inner diameter) filled with 2% liquid agar. After agar solidification, the phantom was scanned. MR imaging was carried out on a 7.0 T high field preclinical MRI scanner (Bruker BioSpec 70/30 small animal MR scanner, Bruker Biospin, Ettlingen, Germany). T_2 relaxation times were obtained by using a multi slice multi echo (MSME) MRI protocol with 20 echo times (TE) ranging from 14 to 280 ms with 14 ms increments, repetition time (TR) = 5000 ms, 2 averages, matrix = 258×258 . For T_1 mapping, a spin echo MRI sequence with slice selective inversion recovery was used with the following parameters: TE = 7.45 ms, TR = 10000 ms, inversion times (TI) = 50–5500 ms, matrix = 128×128 . All MRI scans were acquired in axial orientation, contain 5 slices of 1 mm thickness with a 1 mm gap between slices and a field of view (FOV) = 60×60 mm.

2.5.2. Preparation of cell viability assay

The cytotoxicity of GNPs and MGMPs were performed using the RealTime-Glo MT cell viability assay from Promega. Mouse mesenchymal stem cells (mMSCs) were seeded into 96-well plate with a density of $3 \cdot 10^3$ cells per well in a final volume of 200 μl of DMEM medium supplemented with 15% FBS and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. After incubation of cells with GNPs or MGMPs at different concentrations (10, 25, 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), cell viability was evaluated at different times (4, 8, 24 and 48h) according to the manufacturer's instructions, with minor changes. Three replicates were measured per condition. Values were expressed as relative cell viability respect to the control as mean \pm SD. Comparisons between the groups at different time points were performed using a two-way repeated-measures ANOVA with Bonferroni correction.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthetic procedure for nanoparticles preparation

3.1.1. Optimization and characterization of gelatin nanoparticles (GNPs) by 1-step desolvation method

Desolvation is a thermodynamically driven process for self-assembling polymers into nanoparticles, which depends on a large set of formulation parameters like polymer concentration, pH, amount of desolvating agent, concentration of crosslinking agent, and temperature. Optimizing this route to achieve size control, requires a systematic synthetic study and a careful selection of the conditions to produce size controlled nanoparticles. After a detailed bibliographic review for screening the wide spectrum of conditions found in the literature, we have addressed a sequential process for analyzing the effect of the main formulation parameters, as it has been schematized in figure 1.

First, with the goal of obtaining a small (around 100nm) and homogeneous population of GNPs and attending to the presence of aggregates usually found when preparing NPs [48], a specially homogenous gelatin

Table 1. DLS Characterization of GNPs at different gelatin concentrations.

[gelatin] (mg ml ⁻¹)	Size (nm)	PDI	Zpotential (mV)
10	116.80 ± 0.14	0.14	-5.69 ± 0.7
20	150.25 ± 4.45	0.18	-3.18 ± 0.56
30	201.3 ± 39.88	0.18	-3.65 ± 0.84
40	245	0.14	-3.41 ± 0.22
50		aggregation	

with narrow molecular weight distribution was used (Gelita PH3226). In this way, the first step of the procedure could be avoided, allowing to a first optimization of the modified 1-step desolvation method.

The most important parameter regarding the mechanisms of helix formation in gelatin, as most reversible polymeric gelling systems, is the concentration, which defines three different scaling regimes (dilute, semidilute unentangled, and entangled) [49]. At very low concentrations, (<10 mg ml⁻¹), the helix formation happens mainly at intramolecular level, forming micelles and small particles, while at increasing concentrations, (>10 mg ml⁻¹, semidilute unentangled limit), intermolecular helix begin to form, giving rise to a slow gelling process that creates tenuous 3D networks [50]. For higher concentrations of gelatin, (entangled regime), the density of entanglements, increases in an exponential way, allowing a fast gelling process and the creation of a robust 3D network gel [50].

Therefore, with the aim of producing GNPs with controlled size, we have selected a concentration range, between 10–50 mg ml⁻¹, that stands in between the semidilute unentangled and low entangled regime limits. So, our initial effort was focused on performing a systematic variation of the water phases containing 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 mg ml⁻¹ of gelatin, while the rest of formulation parameters were kept constant as indicated in section 2.2.1. As shown in table 1, individually dispersed nanometric particles of gelatin were obtained from 10 to 30 mg ml⁻¹, while at 40 mg ml⁻¹ two of the three replicates presented aggregation at the following day, nanoparticles prepared at 50 mg ml⁻¹ resulted in visually observed macroscopic aggregation. These data confirms that the low concentration range (10–30 mg ml⁻¹), precluded the formation of a 3D macroscopic gelatin gel, and avoided as well the unwanted formation of a polydisperse sample (PDI < 0.2).

Moreover, it is shown in figure 2 that the size of the so obtained GNPs with increasing gelatin concentration follows a linear relationship. This tendency is in agreement with other works that show an increment in the particle size with the concentration of gelatin [37, 51], and it is a clear indication that semidiluted regime conditions are the optimum for ensuring control in the production of GNPs.

According to our objective of obtaining small GNPs, the lowest gelatin concentrations tested, 10 and 20 mg ml⁻¹, were selected to carry on with the following steps of the optimization procedure. As the next step, adjustment of pH of the aqueous phase was performed to analyze its effect on nanoparticles formation, (2.5, 3.5, 4.5, 10.5, 11.5 and 12.5). To this end, different amounts of HCl 1M or NaOH 1M, were added to the aqueous phase to scan the effect from very acidic to very basic conditions, respectively.

GNPs particles only could be obtained at a pH of 2.5 and 3.5 while for the moderate acidic and all basic pHs, the mixture was completely aggregated. The pH of the aqueous phase plays an important role in nanoparticle

Table 2. DLS characterization of GNPs at different pH using a gelatin concentration of 10 and 20 mg ml⁻¹.

[gelatin] (mg ml ⁻¹)	pH	Size (nm)	PDI	Zpotential (mV)
10	2.5	116.80 ± 0.14	0.14	-5.69 ± 0.70
	3.5		No pellet	
20	2.5	150.25 ± 4.45	0.18	-3.18 ± 0.56
	3.5	115.15 ± 10.96	0.22	-2.12 ± 0.15

Table 3. DLS characterization of GNPs adding the desolvation agent as a bulk or by injection.

Desolvation agent addition mode	Size (nm)	PDI	Zpotential (mV)
Bulk	115.15 ± 10.96	0.22	-2.12 ± 0.15
Injection	110.10 ± 5.09	0.03	-5.06 ± 1.25

Table 4. DLS characterization of GNPs at different temperatures of the water phase

Temperature of water phase (°C)	Size (nm)	PDI	Zpotential (mV)
25		No pellet	
30	91.36 ± 7.53	0.08	-4.35 ± 2.86
37	97.07 ± 6.20	0.09	-4.57 ± 2.19
50	110.10 ± 5.09	0.03	-5.06 ± 1.25

formation since it controls the electrostatic charge of the molecule, essential for promoting electrostatic repulsion between gelatin molecules leading to a controlled precipitation in the form of nanoparticles and therefore, preventing aggregation during desolvation process [15, 19, 34]. Comparison of GNPs obtained at these pHs (2.5 and 3.5) are shown in table 2. Nanoparticles produced at pH 2.5 and 10 mg ml⁻¹ are 116nm in size, whereas when increasing the pH up to 3.5, nanoparticles couldn't be isolated by centrifugation, probably due to their small size. In addition to this, when comparing GNPs obtained at 20 mg ml⁻¹, it can be observed a slight reduction on size in favour of pH 3.5 respected to pH 2.5. These data are consistent with the work of Ahsan *et al* [34] and Shutava *et al* [26], who found a minimum size for GNPs prepared at a pH close to 3.5. The increment in nanoparticle size at lower pH could be propiciated by an increase in the interaction of the

Table 5. DLS characterization of GNPs with volume ratio water phase: desolvation agent.

$V_{\text{water}}/V_{\text{acetone}}$	Size (nm)	PDI	Zpotential (mV)
1:2		No pellet	
1:3	97.07 ± 6.20	0.09	-4.57 ± 2.19
1:4	97.86 ± 4.70	0.13	-2.95 ± 0.37
1:4.5	119.45 ± 8.70	0.15	-1.13 ± 0.79
1:5	120.20 ± 5.29	0.24	-3.24 ± 0.33

hydrophilic segments of gelatin with water molecules. Attending to this, a pH of the aqueous phase of 3.5 and a concentration of 20 mg ml⁻¹ were selected as optimal conditions for next step.

Next step, we evaluated the effect of adding the desolvation solvent (acetone) by abruptly pouring the whole volume (bulk) or through a controlled dropping with a needle syringe (injection). In both cases, the characterization in terms of size is very similar as it can be seen in table 3, however the decrease in the polydispersion index (0.03 versus 0.22), suggests the addition of acetone in a more controlled manner, led to the production of a more homogeneous population. Therefore, the addition of desolvation agent by injection was selected as optimal condition.

Next, we have addressed the effect of temperature of the aqueous phase as a crucial parameter in the mechanism of gelation. First, gelatin was dissolved at 37 °C, since it is not possible to dissolve it at room temperature. Then the desolvation step was performed at 25, 30, 37 and 50 °C using a silicone bath thermostated at these temperatures. As we can see in table 4, nanoparticle size increases with the temperature of the aqueous phase, fitting again these data to a regression line (figure 3).

Moreover, like NPs produced at 10 mg ml⁻¹ and pH 3.5, the lack of a nanoparticle pellet after centrifugation for NPs produced at 25 °C points to a very small size, which difficults the isolation of the nanoparticles under these conditions. In addition to this, GNPs produced at 30 °C were also difficult to isolate, resulting in a very small pellet after centrifugation which led us to select a temperature of 37 °C for the purpose of producing a population with small size but still easily to isolate at lab scale. In addition, 37 °C is the physiological human temperature, hence, the possible association of therapeutic biomolecules or drugs to GNPs could be done without risk of damage or degradation. Most references uses temperatures of 40 °C or higher for preparing gelatin nanoparticles [34–37, 52], among the few works that evaluate the effect of water phase temperature on nanoparticle size, there is no consensus; the work of Shirzad *et al* [33] shows a size increment with the temperature, on the contrary a doctoral dissertation [53] finds a minimum size when working at 50 °C. Probably, the heterogeneous nature of gelatin is the responsible of the diversity in the experimental conditions employed for nanoparticle preparation.

The optimization of the desolvation agent volume was studied using different water/desolvation agent volume ratios (1:2, 1:3, 1:4, 1:4.5 and 1:5). We have focused our efforts in optimizing this parameter using only acetone as desolvation agent considering that previous works reported that smaller nanoparticles with lower

Figure 5. Size of GNPs measured by DLS according to cross-linker concentration and composition (glutaraldehyde and genipin) (symbols) and exponential regression (dashed lines).

Table 6. DLS characterization of GNPs using glutaraldehyde or genipin at different mass ratio of crosslinker and gelatin.

	Mass ratio crosslinker:gelatin	Size (nm)	PDI	Zpotential (mV)
Glutaraldehyde	0.089	136.95 ± 16.62	0.09	-4.06 ± 0.72
	0.179	97.07 ± 6.20	0.09	-4.57 ± 2.19
	0.268	92.67 ± 3.08	0.05	-3.26 ± 0.40
Genipin	0.357	98.87 ± 6.41	0.07	-3.36 ± 0.60
	0.179	366.25 ± 262.69	0.21	5.08 ± 0.72
	0.357	379.65 ± 299.74	0.21	3.55 ± 0.99
	0.714	257.45 ± 148.98	0.17	3.65 ± 0.15
	1.429	296.1 ± 154.43	0.07	4.01 ± 0.81
	2.857	204.9 ± 189.01	0.03	3.89 ± 0.54
	5.714	186.9 ± 202.13	0.07	4.51 ± 0.20

polydispersity index are obtained with acetone compared with other desolvation agents [19, 33, 54]. Table 5 and figure 4 shows respectively the DLS characterization and the corresponding mathematical fitting of the resulted nanoparticles prepared in these conditions.

As acetone is the responsible of the controlled nanoprecipitation of gelatin, it is expected a minimum quantity required for nanoparticle formation. The formulation prepared with a volume ratio 1:2 shows a completely transparent appearance without hint of turbidity or opalescence and no pellet appears after isolation process, hence a volume ratio of 1:3 seems to be necessary for starting nanoparticle formation. Apart of this, there is hardly a difference between nanoparticle size obtained with a volume ratio of 1:3 and 1:4. However, when a volume ratio 1:4.5 is used, a moderated increase in the size and PDI occurs.

The relation between NPs size and acetone volume fits to a sigmoidal regression as it can be observed in figure 4. The range that ensures the production of the smallest NPs lays between volume ratios 1:3 and 1:4, as reported other works [33, 36, 37, 55]. In our case, a volume ratio water phase:acetone 1:3 was selected since is the minimum quantity that allow to obtain nanoparticles of adequate characteristics.

Finally, the crosslinker agent used for nanoparticles preparation, as well as its concentration was evaluated. Until now, a mass ratio 0.179 of glutaraldehyde:gelatin was used for crosslinking reaction. Among the many available crosslinking agents, such as different aldehydes, genipin, carbodiimides in conjunction with N-Hydroxysuccinimide or microbial transglutaminase, glutaraldehyde has found the widest application [56].

This aldehyde is a very potent crosslinker agent even at low concentrations and many works report the use of glutaraldehyde for the preparation of GNPs using mass ratio of crosslinking over gelatin from 0.02 to 1 [33–37, 55], nevertheless, natural origin crosslinkers like genipin, a hydrolysis product of geniposide extracted from gardenia fruits, are generating high interest since it presents reduced toxicity compared with glutaraldehyde [39]. For this reason, in this work, crosslinking reaction with glutaraldehyde and with genipin is compared. It is necessary to clarify that the optimum pH for the crosslinking reaction with genipin is around 7. However, it is not possible to prepare GNPs at a pH near the isoelectric point of the protein (pH 4.8–5) [15]. Therefore, the crosslinking reaction with genipin was performed for 7 days, since after one day the pellet obtained after isolation could not be dispersed, similar to obtained when no crosslinked was used.

As it can be observed in table 6, for any condition of glutaraldehyde a population below 140nm is obtained with very low polydispersity index, in addition, from a mass ratio of 0.179, used in the previous experiments, the NPs' size keeps constant with a value slightly below 100nm. In contrast, even using very high concentrations of genipin (mass ratio genipin:gelatin (5.714)), the average size of the nanoparticles is hardly reduced below 200nm. Moreover, NPs crosslinked with genipin are not reproducible, and a high variability between replicates occurs. Therefore, the crosslinking with glutaraldehyde using a mass ratio of 0.179 was maintained as optimal condition. Compared with the preparation of glutaraldehyde-crosslinked gelatin nanoparticles by desolvation method produced in other works [33, 34, 55], our conditions allow us to obtain a smaller size (98nm versus 112, 125 or 150nm). In addition to this, the work of Taheri Qazvini [31] makes a comparison between different crosslinkers, EDC/NHS and glutaraldehyde, finding a size reduction in favor of EDC/NHS compared to glutaraldehyde. Although that, with the conditions used in that study, the GNPs produced presented a size of 184nm, twice the size obtained in the present work. It is noteworthy to mention that strict comparison between different works is not possible due to the different conditions used for each study. Moreover, figure 5 shows the effect of adding different mass ratios of crosslinkers (glutaraldehyde and genipin) on the GNPs size. The inset is a magnification of the effect of using different mass ratios of glutaraldehyde and gelatin. It has to be highlighted that for both crosslinkers, the chemical effect of the crosslinking allows for a good size control of the GNPs, both follow an exponential decay trend, although for glutaraldehyde, the effectivity is much more pronounced.

Overall, the optimized desolvation method presented in this work, allow us to prepare stable and robust GNPs avoiding the first desolvation step. Moreover, the one-step desolvation procedure allows for a large degree of size control, where mainly all the analyzed parameters follow a soft mathematical relationship allowing for fine size tuning and prediction. The nanoparticles obtained with the selected conditions (gelatin concentration of 20 mg ml⁻¹, pH 3.5, 37 °C, addition of a volume ratio aqueous phase:desolvation agent 1:3 by injection and addition of a mass ratio glutaraldehyde:gelatin of 0.179) are monodisperse (PDI 0.09) with an average size below 100nm and a slight negative Zpotential (−4.57mV). In section 3.1.3, the preparation of magnetite loaded gelatin nanoparticles will be addressed using these optimized conditions.

Figure 7. FTIR spectrum of the bare (black pattern), citrate (green pattern), polyacrylic acid (orange pattern), dopamine (wine) and chitosan (blue pattern) coated MNPs, with the characteristic bands as evidence.

Figure 8. Size distribution histograms and TEM micrographs of the uncoated- Fe_3O_4 (a) and Fe_3O_4 functionalized with: polydopamine (b), chitosan (c), citrate (d) and polyacrylic acid (e). Size distribution was performed using Image J software.

3.1.2. Characterization of magnetite nanoparticles (MNPs)

The characterization of the crystalline phases of MNPs was performed by x-ray diffraction. Powder XRD patterns of bare Fe_3O_4 , Fe_3O_4 @Citrate, Fe_3O_4 @PAA, Fe_3O_4 @CS MNPs and Fe_3O_4 @PDA are shown in figure 6. All the diffraction peaks match the nine diffraction peaks at (1 1 1), (2 2 0), (3 1 1), (4 0 0), (4 2 2), (5 1 1), (4 4 0), (6 2 0) and (5 5 3) by comparison with Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS card no. 9-0629), which correspond with an inverse spinel structure crystalline phase of magnetite [57]. In addition, a broad band located between 15° – 30° is observed in the Fe_3O_4 @CS pattern, which corresponds to the chitosan coating [58].

Magnetite NPs were coated with different shell materials to optimize their compatibility with gelatin and gaining size control during the preparation of MGNPs. The effective surface functionalization of the MNPs was measured with FTIR spectra (figure 7). FTIR spectra of all samples show similar absorption bands at 3400 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic peak to the presence of hydroxyl groups from the adsorbed water molecules and attributed to O-H stretching [59], and at 524 cm^{-1} , associated with the stretching vibration of the tetrahedral groups ($\text{Fe}^{3+}-\text{O}^{2-}$) for Fe_3O_4 [60]. Compared to uncoated- Fe_3O_4 NPs, bands at 1373 , 1367 and 1068 cm^{-1} are clearly observed, which are attributed to the stretching modes (asymmetric COO^- , symmetric COO^- and $-\text{CH}_2$,

respectively) groups of citrate [60]. For PAA coated Fe_3O_4 NPs, the bands located at 2923 and 2847 correspond to stretching vibrations of CH_2 (asymmetric and symmetric). Furthermore, the peaks appearing at 1710, 1631, 1549 and 1393 cm^{-1} are assigned to the stretching vibrations ($\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{C}$, asymmetric COO^- and symmetric COO^-) absorption of carboxylic carbonyl group [61]. Chitosan coated Fe_3O_4 NPs show a weak peak at 3454 and 1568 cm^{-1} associated to the presence of amine groups ($-\text{NH}$ stretching and $-\text{NH}$ bending vibrations, respectively). The absorptions band at 2919 , 2848 cm^{-1} are correlated to the asymmetric and symmetric CH_2 stretching of copolymer chitosan, respectively. In addition, two peaks appear around 1634 and 1020 cm^{-1} which prove the presence of the amide group of chitosan ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ stretching vibrations, respectively) [62]. PDA coated Fe_3O_4 FTIR spectra demonstrated the correct polydopamine coating by the presence of absorptions band at 3378 , 2921 , 2871 , 1603 , 1440 and 1052 cm^{-1} , associated at $-\text{NH}$ stretching, $-\text{CH}_2$ (asymmetric and symmetric), $-\text{NH}$ bending, aromatic $-\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching and $-\text{COH}$ symmetric bending vibrations, respectively [63].

Morphology studies by TEM reveals that all the MNPs present quasi-spherical morphology with a medium size around $7\text{--}10\text{ nm}$ (figure 8), while the aggregation behaviour depends on the coating. Citrate and Polyacrylic acid coated MNPs show better dispersion than bare magnetite, Chitosan or Polydopamine modified MNPs.

Thermogravimetric assay was performed to quantify the amount of organic content in magnetite coated NPs. The results showed bare Fe_3O_4 present the lowest organic content as expected, featuring a weight retention

Figure 11. TEM images of Fe_3O_4 @Citrate loaded gelatin NPs.

Table 7. Magnetic properties of the MNPs.

Magnetic nanoparticles	Saturation magnetization	Remanent magnetization	Coercivity
	M_S (emu g^{-1} Fe_3O_4)	M_R (emu g^{-1} Fe_3O_4)	
			H_C (Oe)
Uncoated	66.07	0.61	3.45
PDA	51.71	0.40	5.60
Citrate	68.73	0.83	6.1
PAA	63.04	0.27	1.62
CS	58.49	0.68	5.24

Table 8. DLS characterization of gelatin nanoparticles loaded with different Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles.

Fe_3O_4 NPs	$Z_{\text{potential}}$ (mV)	D_{DLS} (nm)	PDI	Fe_3O_4 @gelatin $Z_{\text{potential}}$ (mV)
Fe_3O_4 nude	-38	228.8 ± 15.3	0.22	-22.00 ± 4.4
Fe_3O_4 @PAA	-36	210.2 ± 12.76	0.12	-28.10 ± 7.21
Fe_3O_4 @chitosan	+12	253.2 ± 83.15	0.23	-20.85 ± 8.41
Fe_3O_4 @citrate	-42.2	160.9 ± 4.41	0.17	-6.99 ± 2.02
Fe_3O_4 @PDA	+28.7	274.0 ± 2.69	0.19	-3.61 ± 0.6

of 94%. Citrate coated Fe_3O_4 and chitosan coated Fe_3O_4 showed a weight retention of 90% and 88% respectively. On the other hand, polyacrylic acid and polydopamine coated Fe_3O_4 featured the highest organic contents with 87 and 55%, respectively, this fact is due to dehydration of adjacent carboxylic groups (PAA) to form anhydrides which is in agreement with the work of Lu [64] and to the degradation of the polymeric PDA coating on the surface [65].

Finally, the magnetic response of the MNPs is presented in figure 9. The saturation magnetization values (M_S) are in the range of 58–69 emu g^{-1} Fe_3O_4 , which are less than the reported value for bulk Fe_3O_4 NPs (92 emu g^{-1} Fe_3O_4), this effect is attributed to the existence of a magnetically dead layer on the surface of nanoparticles [66]. In addition, all the samples show weak hysteresis with low coercivity and remanence magnetization, revealing that the resulting MNPs display superparamagnetic behaviours. Magnetic properties are summarized in table 7.

3.1.3. Preparation and characterization of magnetic gelatin nanoparticles

Magnetite nanoparticles described in the previous section were used for preparing magnetic gelatin nanoparticles (MGNPs) by the desolvation method with the conditions optimized in section 3.1.1. Acetone was added over the water phase containing the gelatin dissolution and the magnetite NPs suspension giving a mixture with milk-brown appearance. This appearance is due to the formation of nanoparticles composed of a gelatin network entrapping the brown-coloured magnetite nanoparticles. Table 8 shows the DLS characterization of the gelatin nanoparticles loaded with different Fe_3O_4 NPs.

Table 9. Magnetic properties of Fe₃O₄@citrate gelatin nanoparticles.

	M _S (emu g ⁻¹ Fe ₃ O ₄)	M _R (emu g ⁻¹ Fe ₃ O ₄)	H _c (Oe)
Fe ₃ O ₄ @citrate NPs	68.86	0.86	6.12
Fe ₃ O ₄ @citrate-gelatin NPs	65.00	2.87	15.99

Magnetic Gelatin NPs could be obtained irrespective of the coating shell material of MNPs and its surface charge which suggest a physical entrapment of the MNPs within the gelatin matrix. As it can be observed in figure 10, it is not possible to obtain a clear regression between the surface charge of MNPs and the average size of the final magnetic loaded gelatin NPs. Although an increasing tendency seems to indicate that higher positive surface charges produce larger particles, other coating materials should be tested to analyze the effect of Zpotential, (from -30 to +10 mV), on the size of GMNPs.

Among these formulations, the one prepared with citrate coated magnetite, preserves the smallest size (160.9 nm), closer to the original formulation and therefore, it was selected for further characterization. TEM images of the Fe₃O₄@citrate loaded gelatin nanoparticles (figure 11) illustrate a different colour intensity between the organic gelatin material and the inorganic magnetic part. The images show spherical particles with homogeneous size distribution, individually dispersed and absence of aggregates.

The percentage of magnetite in the composite nanoparticles was calculated by analyzing the weight of residue left above 790 °C by thermogravimetric assay. According to this, nanoparticles are composed of 37.79% of magnetite whereas the 62.21% of the composition corresponds to the organic material: gelatin, glutaraldehyde, citrate and water.

The magnetic response of MNPs and MG NPs are presented in figure 12 and table 9. The saturated magnetizations (M_s) are 61.38 and 65 emu g⁻¹ for Fe₃O₄@citrate nanoparticles and Fe₃O₄@citrate loaded gelatin nanoparticles respectively, therefore the MG NPs preserve the high magnetic response of Fe₃O₄@citrate NPs.

Moreover, negligible coercivity and absent remanence were observed, this can be ascribed to the superparamagnetic behavior of small magnetite nanoparticles. This feature is critical for biomedical

Figure 14. Relaxivity calculated from T_1 and T_2 -weighted MR images performed at 7.0 T on 2% agar phantoms loaded with defined concentrations of Fe_3O_4 loaded gelatin NPs.

Figure 15. Cell viability relative to untreated mMSCs cells after exposure to GNPs (a) and MGNPs (b) at different NP concentrations. No significant differences were found between the different conditions (two-way repeated-measurements ANOVA with Bonferroni correction).

applications since it prevents particle aggregation and enables easily redispersion of nanoparticles after application of magnetic field [67]. Indeed, the nanoparticles can be easily resuspended in PBS after magnetic isolation. This saturated magnetization value of MGNPs (65 emus/g) is significantly higher than the reported for others magnetite-gelatin nanoparticles aimed to anticancer therapy [68–70], for instance, Yilmaz *et al* [68] use the magnetic hyperthermia capacity, that is proportional to saturation magnetization [71], to improve the release of the anticancer drug cisplatin from magnetite gelatin nanoparticles.

3.2. Biological characterization

3.2.1. MRI performance

Preliminary *in vitro* magnetic resonance imaging tests were performed to assess their suitability as MRI contrast agents. We were using a 7.0 (T) high field preclinical MRI scanner (Bruker BioSpec). Hereby, we have used a phantom consisting of a set of tubes filled with agar and different concentrations of NPs. In figure 13, T_2 -weighted MR images of the agar phantom is shown using bare gelatin NPs as control. MGNPs were tested at defined Fe concentration of 0.00621, 0.0031, 0.0621, 0.31, 0.61.

For the calculation of actual T_2 values, the signal intensity for the highest Fe concentrations was already zero for the first echo time increment, which does not allow reliable calculations of T_2 . Therefore, for the present acquisition parameters (selection of echo times larger than 7 ms), data points corresponding to concentrations higher than 3 mg ml^{-1} of Fe were excluded due to the short relaxation times for the T_2 -weighted image. The corresponding relaxivities, $r_{1,2} = \frac{d(T_{1,2}^{-1})}{d\Phi_{\text{Fe}}}$, were calculated for $[\text{Fe}] < 0.2 \text{ mM}$ (see figure 14) and resulted in the following values $r_2 = 265.5 \text{ (mM}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$ and $r_1 = 6.3 \text{ (mM}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$, with a $r_2/r_1 = 42.14$, indicating that magnetite NPs are well suited contrast agents for T_2 -weighting. The present magnetic gelatin NPs show a relaxivity r_2 superior to commercial contrast agents, such as Resovist or Endorem, show r_2 values from 54 to $185 \text{ L mmol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ depending on the magnetic field (0.47–4.7 T, respectively) [72].

3.2.2. Cell viability assay

Longitudinal (for up to 48 h) cell viability assay allowed a practical approach to compare the biocompatibility of the GNPs and MGNPs in cell culture media. Determination of survival of mMSCs cells after exposition to these NPs, revealed that none of them were toxic at any concentration tested (10, 25, 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) with a higher cell proliferation observed in GNPs, as it can be observed in figure 15. However, although not statistically significant, apoptosis tends to increase at high MGNPs concentrations (100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), as shown by the slight reduction in the cell survival in comparison to untreated cells. Nevertheless, the percentage of cell viability measured with the MGNPs at different incubation times tested, does not fall under 80% in any case, this value is typically established as a threshold for determining whether a system is toxic in a cell line [73].

Furthermore, previous works have demonstrated the important role played by NPs surface charge in the interaction of NPs with cell membrane, being positive surface charge generally recognized as more cytotoxic [74, 75]. In our case, the gelatin coating provides slightly negative surface charge to the NPs. This surface charge density increased the number of alive mMSC cells.

Compared with other toxicity cellular studies of GNPs and biocompatible polymers coated MNPs, both GNPs and MGNPs presented in this work exhibited negligibly low levels of cytotoxicity. This good biocompatibility demonstrated in cell viability results, allow for its possible applications in Nanobiomedicine, the administration of a high amount of nanoparticles with the consequent increase in the theragnostic power that these NPs can generate.

4. Conclusions

In the present work, gelatin, an extensively used product in pharmaceutical, cosmetics, and food products, has been selected as host matrix to produce controlled theragnostic agents. Following a sequential process for the optimization of the main formulation parameters by 1-step desolvation method, size controlled gelatin nanoparticles were obtained. The systematic variation of the chemical conditions allows to establish a mathematical relationship between the size of the so obtained GNPs and mainly all the analyzed parameters, which in turn, enables a fine size tuning and prediction. This resulted in the preparation of an optimized GNPs population with an average size below 100 nm. Moreover, the controlled incorporation of different Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles within the gelatin nanoparticles was successfully addressed in these optimized conditions, irrespective of the coating shell nature or surface charge of MNPs (from -38 mV to +28 mV), showing that gelatin is a versatile host matrix for the physical entrapment of differently coated NPs. From all the obtained MGNPs, Fe_3O_4 @citrate loaded gelatin nanoparticles, were selected to undergo biological tests, due to their superparamagnetic behavior, high saturation magnetization about 65 (emu g^{-1}) and small size (160nm). In addition to this, the proof of concept of its application as MRI contrast agent showed a good contrast for T_2 weighting MRI, $r_2 = 265.5(\text{mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1})$, superior to the commercial products, such as Resovist[®] or Endorem[®]. Moreover, the viability cellular study revealed that neither GNPs nor MGNPs were toxic at the maximum concentration tested (100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) in mesenchymal stem cells. All these features evidence that gelatin is a versatile and biocompatible host matrix at the nanoscale, capable of harboring of NPs with different chemical surface which allows for the development of multimodal theragnostic agents.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Commission under the PANA project, Call H2020-NMP-2015-two-stage, Grant 686009, BOW project, FETPROACT-EIC-05-2019, Grant 952183 and partially supported by the Consellería de Educación Program for the Development of Strategic Grouping in Materials - AEMAT at the University of Santiago de Compostela under Grant No. ED431E2018/08, Xunta de Galicia.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

ORCID iDs

C Teijeiro-Valiño <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1838-1764>

M A González Gómez <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6234-228X>

S Belderbos <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4043-6007>

W Gsell <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2060-8895>

References

- [1] Vajtai R 2013 Science and engineering of nanomaterials *Springer Handbook of Nanomaterials*. Berlin, Heidelberg ed R Vajtai (Berlin Heidelberg: Springer) pp 1–36
- [2] Zinatloo-Ajabshir S, Morassaei M S, Amiri O and Salavati-Niasari M 2020 Green synthesis of dysprosium stannate nanoparticles using *Ficus carica* extract as photocatalyst for the degradation of organic pollutants under visible irradiation *Ceram. Int.* **46** 6095–107
- [3] Heidari-Asil S A, Zinatloo-Ajabshir S, Amiri O and Salavati-Niasari M 2020 Amino acid assisted-synthesis and characterization of magnetically retrievable ZnCo₂O₄–Co₃O₄ nanostructures as high activity visible-light-driven photocatalyst *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **45** 22761–74
- [4] Putnam W P, Hobbs R G, Keathley P D, Berggren K K and Kärtner F X 2017 Optical-field-controlled photoemission from plasmonic nanoparticles *Nat. Phys.* **13** 335–9
- [5] Irimpan L, Nampoori V P N, Radhakrishnan P, Deepthy A and Krishnan B 2007 Size dependent fluorescence spectroscopy of nanocolloids of ZnO *J. Appl. Phys.* **102** 063524
- [6] Piñero Y, González Gómez M, de Castro Alves L, Arrosa Prieto A, García Acevedo P, Seco Gudiña R, Puig J, Teijeiro C, Yáñez Vilar S and Rivas J 2020 Hybrid nanostructured magnetite nanoparticles: from bio-detection and theragnostics to regenerative medicine *Magnetochemistry*. **6** 4
- [7] Howes P D, Chandrawati R and Stevens M M 2014 Colloidal nanoparticles as advanced biological sensors *Science* **346** 1247390
- [8] Ramos-Cabrer P and Campos F 2013 Liposomes and nanotechnology in drug development: focus on neurological targets *Int J Nanomedicine*. **8** 951–60
- [9] Anselmo A C and Mitragotri S 2019 Nanoparticles in the clinic: an update *Bioeng. Transl. Med.* **4** 1–16
- [10] Campani V, Giarra S and De Rosa G 2018 Lipid-based core-shell nanoparticles: evolution and potentialities in drug delivery *OpenNano*. **3** 5–17
- [11] Wang and XJ Y- 2015 Current status of superparamagnetic iron oxide contrast agents for liver magnetic resonance imaging *World J Gastroenterol.* **21** 13400–2
- [12] NanoTherm Available online: https://www.magforce.com/en/home/our_therapy/ (accessed on 3 Octobre 2020)
- [13] Lee D E, Koo H, Sun I C, Ryu J H, Kim K and Kwon I C 2012 Multifunctional nanoparticles for multimodal imaging and theragnosis *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **41** 2656–72
- [14] Domenico Lombardo P C, Maria Teresa C, Salvatore M and Mikhail Alekseyevich K 2019 Colloidal stability of liposomes *AIMS Materials Science*. **6** 200–13
- [15] Elzoghby A O 2013 Gelatin-based nanoparticles as drug and gene delivery systems: Reviewing three decades of research *J. Controlled Release* **172** 1075–91
- [16] Wang H, Boerman O C, Sariibrahimoglu K, Li Y, Jansen J A and Leeuwenburgh S C G 2012 Comparison of micro- vs. nanostructured colloidal gelatin gels for sustained delivery of osteogenic proteins: Bone morphogenetic protein-2 and alkaline phosphatase *Biomaterials* **33** 8695–703
- [17] Zwioerek K, Kloeckner J, Wagner E and Coester C 2005 Gelatin nanoparticles as a new and simple gene delivery system *J Pharm Pharm Sci.* **7** 22–8 <https://europepmc.org/article/med/15850545>
- [18] Foox M and Zilberman M 2015 Drug delivery from gelatin-based systems *Expert Opinion on Drug Delivery.* **12** 1547–63
- [19] Sahoo N, Sahoo R K, Biswas N, Guha A and Kuotsu K 2015 Recent advancement of gelatin nanoparticles in drug and vaccine delivery *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **81** 317–31
- [20] Cascone M G, Lazzeri L, Carmignani C and Zhu Z 2002 Gelatin nanoparticles produced by a simple W/O emulsion as delivery system for methotrexate *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Med.* **13** 523–6
- [21] Bajpai A K and Choubey J 2006 Design of gelatin nanoparticles as swelling controlled delivery system for chloroquine phosphate *J. Mater. Sci., Mater. Med.* **17** 345–58
- [22] Bajpai A K and Choubey J 2006 *In vitro* release dynamics of an anticancer drug from swellable gelatin nanoparticles *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **101** 2320–32
- [23] Zinatloo-Ajabshir S and Taheri Qazvini N 2014 Inverse miniemulsion method for synthesis of gelatin nanoparticles in presence of CDI/NHS as a non-toxic cross-linking system *Journal of Nanostructures.* **4** 267–75 https://jns.kashanu.ac.ir/article_7969.html
- [24] Zhao Y-Z et al 2012 Experiment on the feasibility of using modified gelatin nanoparticles as insulin pulmonary administration system for diabetes therapy *Acta Diabetologica.* **49** 315–25
- [25] Ai H, Jones S A and Lvov Y M 2003 Biomedical applications of electrostatic layer-by-layer nano-assembly of polymers, enzymes, and nanoparticles *Cell Biochemistry and Biophysics.* **39** 23
- [26] Shutava T G et al 2009 Layer-by-layer-coated gelatin nanoparticles as a vehicle for delivery of natural polyphenols *ACS Nano.* **3** 1877–85
- [27] Li W-M, Liu D-M and Chen S-Y 2011 Amphiphilically-modified gelatin nanoparticles: Self-assembly behavior, controlled biodegradability, and rapid cellular uptake for intracellular drug delivery *J. Mater. Chem.* **21** 12381–8
- [28] Won Y W, Yoon S M, Sonn C H, Lee K M and Kim Y H 2011 Nano self-assembly of recombinant human gelatin conjugated with α -tocopheryl succinate for Hsp90 inhibitor, 17-AAG, delivery *ACS Nano.* **5** 3839–48
- [29] Coester Klhvbjk C J 2000 Gelatin nanoparticles by two step desolvation a new preparation method, surface modifications and cell uptake *J. Microencapsulation* **17** 187–93
- [30] Zinatloo-Ajabshir S and Taheri Qazvini N 2015 Effect of some synthetic parameters on size and polydispersity index of gelatin nanoparticles cross-linked by CDI/NHS system *Journal of Nanostructures.* **5** 137–44 https://jns.kashanu.ac.ir/article_10315.html
- [31] Qazvini N T and Zinatloo S 2011 Synthesis and characterization of gelatin nanoparticles using CDI/NHS as a non-toxic cross-linking system *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Med.* **22** 63–9
- [32] Elzoghby A O, Samy W M and Elgindy N A 2012 Protein-based nanocarriers as promising drug and gene delivery systems *J. Control. Release* **161** 38–49
- [33] Azarmi S et al 2006 Optimization of a two-step desolvation method for preparing gelatin nanoparticles and cell uptake studies in 143B osteosarcoma cancer cells *J Pharm Pharm Sci.* **9** 124–32 <https://europepmc.org/article/med/16849014>
- [34] Ahsan S M and Rao C M 2017 The role of surface charge in the desolvation process of gelatin: implications in nanoparticle synthesis and modulation of drug release *Int J Nanomedicine.* **12** 795–808
- [35] Khan S A and Schneider M 2013 Nanoprecipitation Versus two step Desolvation Technique for the Preparation of Gelatin Nanoparticles *Colloidal Nanocrystals for Biomedical Applications VIII SPIE BiOS* Volume 8595 (California, United States of America, 2013) (<https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2002419>)
- [36] Abdelrady H, Hathout R M, Osman R, Saleem I and Mortada N D 2019 Exploiting gelatin nanocarriers in the pulmonary delivery of methotrexate for lung cancer therapy *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* **133** 115–26

- [37] Shamarekh K S, Gad H A, Soliman M E and Sammour O A 2020 Towards the production of monodisperse gelatin nanoparticles by modified one step desolvation technique *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. **50** 189–200
- [38] Song F, Zhang L-M, Yang C and Yan L 2009 Genipin-crosslinked casein hydrogels for controlled drug delivery *Int. J. Pharm.* **373** 41–7
- [39] Manickam B, Nair R and Elumalai M 2014 ‘Genipin’—The natural water soluble cross-linking agent and its importance in the modified drug delivery systems: an overview. *current Drug Deliv.* **11** 139
- [40] Fuchs S, Kutscher M, Hertel T, Winter G, Pietzsch M and Coester C 2010 Transglutaminase: new insights into gelatin nanoparticle cross-linking *J. Microencapsulation* **27** 747–54
- [41] Kumari A, Yadav S K and Yadav S C 2010 Biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles based drug delivery systems *Colloids Surf., B* **75** 1–18
- [42] Coester C (ed) 2004 New biocompatible nanoparticles based on fractionized gelatin as drug delivery systems for nucleic acids and peptides 2004 *Int. Conf. on MEMS, NANO and Smart Systems (ICMENS'04)* 200425–27 Aug (<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMENS.2004.1508914>)
- [43] Sellmeyer D J, Liu Y and Shindo D 2006 *Handbook of Advanced Magnetic Materials*. (New York, NY: Tingshua University Press) Chapter 1.978-1-4020-7984-9
- [44] Laurent S, Bridot J-L, Elst L V and Muller R N 2010 Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles for biomedical applications *Future Medicinal Chemistry*. **2** 427–49
- [45] Vallabani N V S and Singh S 2018 Recent advances and future prospects of iron oxide nanoparticles in biomedicine and diagnostics *Biotech.* **8** 279
- [46] Massart R 1981 Preparation of aqueous magnetic liquids in alkaline and acidic media *IEEE Trans. Magn.* **17** 1247–8
- [47] González-Gómez M A et al 2019 Development of superparamagnetic nanoparticles coated with polyacrylic acid and aluminum hydroxide as an efficient contrast agent for multimodal imaging *Nanomaterials*. **9** 1626
- [48] Marty J J, Oppenheim R C and Speiser P 1978 Nanoparticles—a new colloidal drug delivery system *Pharm. Acta Helv.* **53** 17–23 <https://europepmc.org/article/med/643885>
- [49] Rubinstein M and Dobrynin A V 1999 Associations leading to formation of reversible networks and gels *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science*. **4** 83–7
- [50] Guo L, Colby R H, Lusignan C P and Howe A M 2003 Physical gelation of gelatin studied with rheo-optics *Macromolecules* **36** 10009–20
- [51] Won Y-W and Kim Y-H 2008 Recombinant human gelatin nanoparticles as a protein drug carrier *J. Controlled Release* **127** 154–61
- [52] Subara D, Jaswir I, Alkhatib M F R and Noorbacha I A 2018 Synthesis of fish gelatin nanoparticles and their application for the drug delivery based on response surface methodology. *Advances in Natural Sciences: Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*. **9** 045014
- [53] Zwiroek K 2006 *Gelatin Nanoparticles as Delivery System for Nucleotide-Based Drugs* LMU München: Fakultät für Chemie und Pharmazie <https://edoc.ub.uni-muenchen.de/6356/>
- [54] Huang J-Y, Liu C-C, Yen K-C, Kang P-L, Sadhasivam S and Lin F-H 2012 Choleminchloride hydrochloride-cationized gelatin/calcium-phosphate nanoparticles as gene carriers for transgenic chicken production *Process Biochem.* **47** 1919–25
- [55] Subara D, Jaswir I, Alkhatib M F R and Noorbacha I A N 2017 Process optimization for the production of fish gelatin nanoparticles *International Food Research Journal*. **24** S501–7
- [56] Migneault I, Dartiguenave C, Bertrand M J and Waldron K C 2004 Glutaraldehyde: behavior in aqueous solution, reaction with proteins, and application to enzyme crosslinking *BioTechniques*. **37** 790–802
- [57] Kimura S M L C, Manghnani H M and Nakagiri N 1986 *Phys. Chem. Miner.* 238–44
- [58] Kumar S, Dutta P K and Koh J 2011 A physico-chemical and biological study of novel chitosan–chloroquinoline derivative for biomedical applications *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **49** 356–61
- [59] Li Y-S, Church J S and Woodhead A L 2012 Infrared and Raman spectroscopic studies on iron oxide magnetic nano-particles and their surface modifications *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **324** 1543–50
- [60] Nalbandian L, Patrikiadou E, Zaspalis V, Patrikidou A, Hatzidaki E and Papandreou N C 2016 Magnetic nanoparticles in medical diagnostic applications: synthesis, characterization and proteins conjugation *Current Nanoscience*. **12** 455–68
- [61] Silverstein B H R M, Bassler G C and Morrill T C 1992 *Spectrometric identification of organic compounds*. Wiley, Chichester, 1991 *Magn. Reson. Chem.* **30** (Chichester: Wiley) 364-0 471 63404 2
- [62] Dong Y, Xu C, Wang J, Wang M, Wu Y and Ruan Y 2001 Determination of degree of substitution for N-acylated chitosan using IR spectra. *Science in China Series B: Chemistry*. **44** 216–24
- [63] Andrade M F C, Parussulo A L A, Netto C G C M, Andrade L H and Toma H E 2016 Lipase immobilized on polydopamine-coated magnetite nanoparticles for biodiesel production from soybean oil *Biofuel Research Journal*. **3** 403–9
- [64] Lu P and Hsieh Y-L 2009 Cellulose nanocrystal-filled poly(acrylic acid) nanocomposite fibrous membranes *Nanotechnology* **20** 415604
- [65] Davodi B, Jahangiri M and Ghorbani M 2019 Magnetic Fe₃O₄@ polydopamine biopolymer: Synthesis, characterization and fabrication of promising nanocomposite *J. Vinyl Add. Tech.* **25** 41–7
- [66] Wallyn J, Anton N and Vandamme T F 2019 Synthesis, principles, and properties of magnetite nanoparticles for *in vivo* imaging applications—a review *Pharmaceutics*. **11** 1–29
- [67] Dorniani D, Hussein M Z B, Kura A U, Fakurazi S, Shaari A H and Ahmad Z 2012 Preparation of Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles coated with gallic acid for drug delivery *Int J Nanomedicine*. **7** 5745–56
- [68] Yilmaz H and Sanlier S H 2013 Preparation of magnetic gelatin nanoparticles and investigating the possible use as chemotherapeutic agent *Artificial Cells, Nanomedicine, and Biotechnology*. **41** 69–77
- [69] Choubey J and Bajpai A K 2010 Investigation on magnetically controlled delivery of doxorubicin from superparamagnetic nanocarriers of gelatin crosslinked with genipin *J. Mater. Sci., Mater. Med.* **21** 1573–86
- [70] Sirivat A and Paradee N 2019 Facile synthesis of gelatin-coated Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle: Effect of pH in single-step co-precipitation for cancer drug loading *Mater. Des.* **181** 107942
- [71] Abenojar E C, Wickramasinghe S, Bas-Concepcion J and Samia A C S 2016 Structural effects on the magnetic hyperthermia properties of iron oxide nanoparticles *Progress in Natural Science: Materials International*. **26** 440–8
- [72] Rohrer M, Bauer H, Mintonovitch J, Requardt M and Weinmann H J 2005 Comparison of magnetic properties of MRI contrast media solutions at different magnetic field strengths *Invest Radiol.* **40** 715–24
- [73] López-García J, Lehoeký M, Humpolíček P and Sába P 2014 HaCaT Keratinocytes response on antimicrobial atelocollagen substrates: extent of cytotoxicity, cell viability and proliferation *Journal of Functional Biomaterials*. **5** 43–57
- [74] Arvizo R R et al 2010 Effect of nanoparticle surface charge at the plasma membrane and beyond *Nano Lett.* **10** 2543–8
- [75] Yan J et al 2018 The effect of surface charge on the cytotoxicity and uptake of carbon quantum dots in human umbilical cord derived mesenchymal stem cells *Colloids Surf B Biointerfaces*. **171** 241–9